

Anodization of Zircaloy-4 in 0.1M KOH in Presence of Halide Ions

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The effect of halide ions on the kinetics of anodisation of zircaloy-4 in 0.1 M KOH have been studied at a constant current density of 4 mA cm^{-2} and at room temperature. At higher concentrations of halide ions ($\geq 0.1 \text{ M}$), there is no film formation and deleterious effects are observed. However, there is film formation and the kinetics of film formation are well studied at lower concentrations of halide ions. However, in the presence of iodide ions, there is a remarkable change in the kinetics of film formation.

ANODISATION of zirconium in various electrolytes have been studied by Young¹, Charlesby², Wilkins³ and also by us^{4,5}. In the present work, an attempt is made to study the effect of halide ions, mainly iodide ions, on the kinetics of anodisation of zircaloy-4 in 0.1 M KOH.

Experimental

Zircaloy-4 specimens (0.150 mm thick) used were a gift sample from Nuclear Fuel Complex, Hyderabad. The nominal analysis (%) given was Sn (1.44), Fe (0.23), Cr (0.07) and Zr (98.26). The procedures for the preparation of the specimens and chemical polishing was given in our earlier paper⁶. Anodisations were carried out in 0.1 M KOH in the presence of various proportions of halide ions at a constant current density of 4 mA cm^{-2} . Thickness of the film formed was estimated by capacitance measurements. The density and dielectric constant of ZrO_2 were taken as 5.7 g ml^{-1} and 24.7, respectively⁷.

The constant current generator used was stabilised power supply, built by instruments Techniques Pvt. Ltd., Hyderabad. A digital LCR meter VL666 supplied by Vasavi Electronics, Hyderabad, was used for the capacitance measurements.

Results and Discussion

The chemically polished zircaloy-4 specimens were anodised in the electrolyte 0.1 M KOH in the presence and absence of halide ions in various proportions at a constant current density of 4 mA cm^{-2} and at room temperature.

In pure KOH the plots of formation voltage vs time and reciprocal capacitance vs time, and reciprocal capacitance vs formation voltage, were

found to be linear upto $95 \pm 5 \text{ V}$ and the corresponding thickness was estimated to be $240 \pm 10 \text{ nm}$. The current efficiency and the differential field of formation were found to be 41.36% and 5.062 MV cm^{-1} , respectively. Beyond this thickness ($240 \pm 10 \text{ nm}$) the current efficiency was found to fall gradually whilst the differential field decreased to 4.04 MV cm^{-1} .

There was no film formation when the ratio of $[\text{KOH}] : [\text{halide ion}] < 10 : 1$, and deleterious effects are observed, such as pitting and precipitation. However, there was film formation when the ratio was $100 : 1$. It is found that there is an increase in the current efficiency and the differential field of formation in the presence of halide ions in 0.1 M KOH and it is shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANODIC FILMS FORMED IN 0.1 M KOH IN PRESENCE AND ABSENCE OF HALIDE IONS

$[\text{KOH}] : [\text{X}^-]^*$	X^-*	Current efficiency (%)	Differential field, (F_D) MV cm^{-1}
100 : 1	F^-	74.68	5.46
100 : 1	Cl^-	55.71	5.24
100 : 1	Br^-	49.78	3.69
100 : 1	I^-	81.12	5.50
10 : 1	I^-	56.00	5.25
1 : 1	I^-	49.00	5.10
0.1 M KOH	—	41.36	5.06

* $\text{X}^- \equiv$ Halide ion.

Addition of iodide ions to 0.1 M KOH showed that there was film formation when the ratio of $[\text{KOH}] : [\text{halide ion}] \geq 1 : 1$. The current efficiency and differential field were found to be increased with the decrease in the proportion of iodide ion in 0.1 M KOH. However, when the concentration

of iodide ions was $> 0.1 M$, there was no film formation and liberation of iodine was observed. The linearity of the plots of formation voltage vs time was increased in the presence of iodide ions and this was shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Formation voltage vs time for anodisation of zircaloy-4 in 0.1 M KOH + various proportions of halide ions: (○) 0.0, (●) 0.1, (□) 0.01 and (△) 0.001 M I⁻.

Sastry⁴ and Sastry and Draper⁸ studied the effect of anion impurities in 0.1 M KOH on the kinetics of anodic film formation on zirconium at a constant current density of 4.1 mA cm⁻² and observed that the current efficiency and the differential field of formation were increased in the presence of anion impurities. They attributed these results to the incorporation of anion impurities into the anodic film and it was confirmed by radio-tracer techniques^{4,8}. Hence, an increase in the current efficiency and the differential field with the addition of halide ions to 0.1 M KOH in the present work may be attributed to the incorporation of halide ions into the anodic film.

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